

**STUDY OF NEURO-LINGUISTICS PROGRAMMING COMPONENTS IN SPEECH-
LITERATURE: A CASE STUDY TO LEGISLATIVE SPEECH OF BHUMIPUTRA BIJU
PATNAIK**

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Abstract

speech is for mass such as a speech in an election campaign by a Politician having high reputation, and then it has the convincing capabilities to influence the common people. And the neuro-linguistic component (NLC) within a speech affects the audience either in positive or in adverse manner. A number of research contribution and conceptual framework developed upon language therapy (Bandler R. and J. Grinder. (1976)), The Myth of Sisyphus (Camus, A. (2012)), Of Grammatology (Derrida, J. (1998)), Communication Process (Sanchez, N. (2012)) has presently resifting the immersing literary area i.e. the scope of 'Speech literature' to many fold. However, either the research limited to applied linguistics or NLP, Psychology or cognitive process and not open the engagement process of both the speaker to its identity vis.-a-vis. relationship with intended speakers to their identity. Therefore, to plug-in such textual components, here we are tried to find out such elements and its influencing peripheral phenomena. And to carry out the pilot mode research, we have taken both the English and Odia version of the Legendary Indian legislator Biju Patanaik's legislative speech as the onboard primary data to reach in a conclusion in an aim to develop a language independent frame-net of neuro-linguistic programming Textual components.

Keywords: Speech literature, Biju Patnaik, Figure of Speech, Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP).

1. Introduction

Speech and speech-literature are two separate phenomena. The live speech of a speaker influence or affects the receiver both in positive and in adverse way. With this if the speaker has some identity attached with him, like teacher, police, judge and or politician; it puts impact to their counterparts. In contrast, if the same speech is a live debate among the legislators for certain bill that is laid on the table, or just an arguments of two Lawyers in favors of their respective clients also affects the psychic impression of the audience present at the ground or convince the decision maker such as the Speaker of the House or the Judicial magistrate on the dais. However, if the speeches are for mass such as a speech in an election campaign by a Politician having high reputation, then it has the convincing capabilities to influence the common people. Unlike a song, an influential speech has also maintained its tempo, rhythm, style and text. But the question arises, what are the neuro-linguistic programming components (NLC) within a speech that affects the audience either in positive or in adverse manner. In other way, the Neuro Linguistic Programming (NLP) Techniques in an influential speech are generally adopting the hypnotic approaches such as representational theory, Milton model, Meta model, anchoring and cognitive reframing etc in order to engage the potential audience to achieve the ultimate goal of the speech. Therefore, the present paper is trying to develop an inter relationship between NLC and NLP that are primary develop the quality of a normal speech to influential speech through the figure of speeches as one such NLC in a speech literature.

2. Speech Literature & Arts of Speech:

An influential speech is always treated as the most effective medium of oral communication and it refers the delivering of message to intended audience by the speaker. Therefore an effective speech always carries certain primary features such as clarity, definiteness, conciseness, informal touch, audience participation and body language. Therefore, in the absence of these primary characteristics, a speech loses its edge. However, except the primary features, the speakers power, position, branding, speaking place and over and above the addressee are also played vital role to convert a normal speech to an influential speech. Therefore

an ideal speech always follows some arts and same time also expects some freedom. When we write down such speeches for future or for intended readers, it becomes defined as Speech-literature. However, the speech-literature never give-up its ambient eco-literary sphere and always expects intended audience and excludes itself from other branch of literature due to its exclusiveness of neuro-linguistic components and features. Therefore, the influential argument of a Lawyer before the Judiciary bench may affects the concerned case counter parts or influences the Hon'ble Judicial magistrate on the Dias but the legislative speech affects the public and the audience directly or indirectly and converts to Vote at the time of election due to its higher neuro-linguistic components (NLC) across the text/speech of the matter.

3. Relationship of Figure of Speech and NLC:

A figure of speech is a word or phrase that has other meaning than its normal definition. In other words, figures of speeches are relied on implied or suggested meaning, rather than a dictionary definition. And a number of Neuro-linguistic or rhetorical techniques are expressed and developed them from it literary specifications such as metaphors and similes to more general forms like sarcasm and slang. The prominent Figurative components within a speech are: Metaphor, Idiom, Proverb, Simile, Oxymoron, Metonym, Irony etc. However, as and when these figurative components overpowered the literary definition of a speech through different Neuro-linguistic components, it express the figurative language such as Sarcasm, Slang etc and generates the convincing power of the same speech for intended audience.

4. Literature Survey:

The term Neuro Linguistic Programming as attached to two primary area of studies i.e. linguistics and brain and behaves as the relational bridge between language and structure and/or function of the nervous system. The scope of the study perhaps a scarier thought for linguistics rather than the syntactic structure or code such as NP, VP, Aux, Subject that a linguist encounter. And perhaps the book 'Language and Mind' (1967) is the first ever deals the contribution of linguistics in the study of human mind. A number of researches have been done in this area. From notion of NLP (Bandler and Grinder, 1975), aspects of phonological impairment in aphasia (Miceli et.al, 1980), lexical-semantic information (Marslen-Wilson, 1987), representing and/or processing phonological information (Liebenthal et al., 2005), The Effect of Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP) on Reading Comprehension (Fahimeh Farahan, 2018) to Hassan Ud-deen (2020) all are tried to find out the NLP components and principles to power up the speech and behavior. However a close observation to NLT yet to be required explicitly for understanding the impact of an influential speech upon intended audience.

5. Experimental Data Set:

To find out the solution of neuro-linguistics programming components in speech-literature, we have taken the selected Legislative speeches of Bhumiputra Biju Patnaik from the book of 'Biju Patnaik (a legislative biography)' authored and compiled by Ramakanta Das, Joint Secretary of Rajya Sabha, the Upper House of the Parliament of India. And the under study covers only the Hon'ble Legislator Biju Patnaik's selected three speeches that are: (1) 'Public Sector Iron & Steel Companies (Restructuring) and miscellaneous Provision Bill delivered as the Minister of Steel & Mines on dated 22nd Dec. 1977', 22nd & 23rd March 1978, (2) Motion of No-confidence in the council of Ministers on dated 10 May 1978, (3) Draught Situation in Orissa on dated 28th Nov. 1996. With this some other legislative discussions and speeches are also taken into consideration to find out the notable NLP components in speech literature. And as going through the Text, the average Figurative Speech Type frequencies are represented in Fig. No 01.

Fig. No. 01: Calculated Figurative Speech Frequency

6. Annotating Neuro-linguistic Textual Components:

Human languages are as the computational system of brain that computes the process of transformation of thoughts to acoustic signals. Therefore an influential speech carries number of neuro-linguistic textual components and affects our body and behavior (programming). Again the described Neuro-linguistic Textual Components (NLTC) are primarily controlled by the above figurative speech components within the text. Therefore the present paper tries out to annotate the NLTC components from above mentioned datasets in order to reach out concluding remarks of impact of NLTC upon speech-literature. In annotating process, we try to cater the different NLT component such as Irony, Sarcasm, Audience attention statements, figure of estimations, and logical conclusions etc from the observed texts. And here are the following classified examples from experimented datasets for better remarks:

a. Irony:

- Now all my friends from Calcutta come and say: 'We are proud Bengalis'. They were only proud fishermen at that time, 200 years back.....

b. Sarcasm:

- As for the son of the soil, if I may tell my Bihar friends....
- You have this party; this wise party here sitting in the opposition, has taken 30 years to unwind yourself and become unwise....
- I said a pack of sycophants. Please look at the dictionary if you could not understand it.

c. Audience Attention statements:

- Shri Yamuna Prasad Shastri has become un duly excited....
- Shastriji please listen carefully....
- A.K. Roy, my old friend, raised certain points...
- I must congratulate Mr. Pai for having made a fruitful speech...

d. Figure of Estimation:

- Hardly 10 million tonnes
- 30,000 permanent employees
- No member of parliament assisted me;
- 9 persons, including a Police head Constable

e. Logical conclusion:

- Therefore, the purpose of putting that company as an appendage or a part of steel plants will not be beneficial to the construction company which employs a large number of people and which has to find work both inside India and outside India.
- Therefore, this house surely would like me to insure that MECON does not die with it.
- Voice of Questions with Argumentative numerical data sets
- What does HSCL do with 30,000 permanent employees which includes thousands of engineers? Disband it? The SAIL cannot give any more work. It was doing work worth Rs100 crores and now it has come down to Rs. 20 crores of work. What does it do? Do I close it? Do I dismiss all the employees?
- If the people have suffered for 30 years, my friend, will not they suffer us?

- f. Address to someone but intended for others
- The Chief Minister and state ministers have gone to Japan xxx Japan is not yesterday's baby. But they go to Tokyo, Korea, Hong Kong, Singapore for a nice long jaunt and here the people are running away from the state.
- g. Immerging and contemporary issues as the theme of the speech:
- China is trying to cut down their population by pursuing 'one child norm'. We have no limit to our children; whether this Prime Minister or that prime Minister or whatever it is, they have ten children, eight children or five children. How can we control?

7. Observable Result:

Based on the objectives of the study, the following research question was addressed: What is the effect of NLP on Speech Literature upon future intended audience rather than the present intended audience? As the study follows the empirical method but quasi-experimental and the study is under controlled data sets, the observed output may vary in large dataset of the same speaker or of different speaker as to context and audience. However, the following unique characteristics are being observed from the controlled legislative speech of legendary legislature 'Biju Patnayak's legislative speech.

- Developed the well planed Images by comparing the different plans of Govt. taking different numerical, historical, scientific or economical and geographical datasets.
- Speech voice and inert message are for the intended audience not the audience at front.
- Attack the opposition with sharp ironical statements.
- Speech voice was very free and open minded.
- The data sets were collected from practical experience
- The speech containing statistical or comparative data sets were convincible.
- Ironical Questionnaires for counterparts that contains the implied but un-expressed Answers
- Sometimes the speeches are addressed to somebody but reflects the target of audience are others.
- Semantic Priming for Clearer Comprehension.
- Picks the immersing and contemporary issues attached to the addressed audience or intended audience emotions and needs.
- The intended message is argumentative with convincible data sets.

Therefore, the art of speech literature of Biju Patanayak is a mixture of (a) the use of metaphors making indirect suggestions (Milton Model), (b) development of creative piece by using unfinished sentences and phrases (Trans-derivational Search (TDS)) but relies on clear and pragmatic language of the speech.

Conclusion:

So, here it can be broadly outlined that irrespective of large areas of NLP are based on observations, an influential speech literature in certain language are mostly subconsciously designed to elicit a response from the subject and, based on this feedback, adjust the manner in which the intended audience proceeds. And only a small part of an influential speech is achieved through what the speaker actually say, but the rest is non-verbal such as gesture, facial expressions, postures, voice qualities etc but hidden within the figure of the speech. Therefore, the figures of the speech embedded in communication are establishing and build rapport of NLC for the reading of nonverbal communications and that exactly happened in the legislative speech of legendary legislator Biju Patanaik. With this, irrespective of the lacks of empirical validity, the NLP components are retaining their recognition at the psychosomatic level of the audience and the primary factor that transfers from the speakers to audience and recognized ultimately the ordinary speech to a credible speech.

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